

Integrating Multi-Source Data to Construct Complete Pedestrian Networks

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Abstract. Accurate pedestrian network modelling is essential for pedestrian dynamics. However, existing pedestrian network datasets are fragmented, lack connectivity and primarily focus on vehicle-oriented infrastructure, which limits their effectiveness for fine-scale pedestrian applications. This study presents a graph-based model that is designed using multiple spatial datasets to enhance pedestrian network construction. This framework is applied in a case study in Taipei City, which produces a promising preliminary pedestrian network compared to the existing pedestrian datasets.

Keywords. Complete Pedestrian Networks, Graph-based Modelling, Multi-source Data Integration, Open Data, Pedestrian Availability.

1. Introduction

Pedestrian networks serve as fundamental frameworks for pedestrian dynamics, which encompass the evaluation of urban infrastructure, pedestrian behaviour, safety and walkability. However, the main disadvantage of existing pedestrian networks is their lack of completeness, which leads to applications such as pedestrian navigation remaining predominantly vehicle-centric. These applications prioritise road networks while overlooking pedestrian-specific pathways.

A sample of the current state of pedestrian networks is shown in Figure 1. Pedestrian infrastructure including footways (brown), marked pedestrian lanes (blue) and sidewalks (orange) is displayed over grey construction blocks in Figure 1(a). Real-world examples for each type of pedestrian infrastructure are provided in Figure 1(b). Regions A and B highlighted in Figure 1(a) present typical issues observed in pedestrian datasets such as missing

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links between adjacent segments and unmapped pedestrian connections at intersections. These problems affect continuity and hinder availability analysis of networks and planning and applications relevant to pedestrians.

These limitations underscore the need for a more flexible and automated approach to pedestrian network modelling. Graph-based methods provide a solution by representing pedestrian pathways as interconnected nodes and edges, which effectively captures formal and informal routes (Jiang & Claramunt 2004, Newman 2018). Thus, we propose a graph-based approach that integrates geographically diverse data sources to support highly automated pedestrian network modelling, with an explicit focus on enhancing network completeness.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Illustration of the current state of pedestrian networks. (a) Datasets of pedestrian infrastructure, such as footways, marked pedestrian lanes and sidewalks; (b) Real-world examples of pedestrian infrastructure (from Google Street View API (Google 2025)).

2. Methodology

2.1. Study Area and Materials

The study area is located in downtown Taipei City, which is known for its diverse pedestrian environments and high availability (Figure 2). The area includes a roundabout and major Metro Taipei (MRT) stations, which serve as a key transit hub with significant pedestrian activity. In addition, it features educational institutions, public parks and commercial zones, which provide a representative mix of residential, commercial and recreational spaces.

Figure 2. Study area (base image: National Land Surveying and Mapping Center, Taiwan; PHOTO2 layer (NLSC)).

The datasets used in this study have been sourced from three authoritative providers:

- 1) **Taipei City Government Open Data** offers open datasets related to pedestrian infrastructure, including sidewalks, marked pedestrian lanes, YouBike stations, bus stops and vehicle roads.
- 2) **RiChi Technology Inc.** supplies detailed geospatial data, such as construction blocks, MRT station boundaries, key landmarks (noted as Mark) and roads.
- 3) **OpenStreetMap (OSM)** provides pedestrian-specific geospatial data, which contains footways and pedestrian paths.

Table 1. Summary of used spatial datasets.

Item	Dataset	Type	Provider
1	Sidewalks	Polygon	Taipei City Government
2	Marked Pedestrian Lanes	Polygon	
3	YouBike Stations	Point	
4	Bus Stops	Point	
5	Vehicle road	Line	

6	Construction blocks	Polygon	RiChi Technology Inc.
7	MRT stations / Coverage	Point / Polygon	
8	Mark	Point	
9	Road	Line	
10	Footway	Line	OSM

2.2. Grid-based Graph Construction

A grid-based graph is used for pedestrian network representation and offers advantages such as scalability and improved connectivity. To facilitate pedestrian network modelling, the study area is divided into a $2\text{m} \times 2\text{m}$ grid, which reflects the typical width of pedestrian sidewalks with 520,380 grids in total. In addition, it enables the model to capture narrow walkways and small-scale urban features effectively.

The centre of each grid serves as a graph node. Each node is assigned attributes based on spatial data sources, including centroid coordinates (x, y), which signify the spatial location of each node, and an availability label (`is_pedestrian`). The label is categorised as follows: 1 (available), -1 (non-available) and 0 (unknown). The ground truth labelling is determined through a rule-based method that integrates multiple spatial datasets.

Grid cells are labelled as available (1) if they intersect with any pedestrian-related datasets, including footways, sidewalks or marked pedestrian lanes. Unlabelled cells that are covered by construction blocks (buildings) or vehicle-only roads are labelled as non-available (-1). This distinction reflects these areas are generally unavailable or unsafe for pedestrian use. Cells that do not overlap with any of the datasets mentioned above are assigned a label of unknown (0). These cells are subsequently modelled using a graph convolution network (GCN) to infer potential pedestrian availability based on the surrounding spatial context. The labelled nodes (i.e., those with values 1 and -1) are randomly split into training, validation, and test sets in a ratio of 6:3:1 for model training and evaluation.

Edges within the pedestrian network establish connections between nodes by considering proximity and available constraints. We use Rook's connectivity rule, which is commonly referred to as the 4-neighbor rule. This rule involves connecting each grid node to its adjacent cells—above, below, to the left and to the right. An edge is established if the current node is available (score = 1) or is located within a neighbourhood with a sufficient number of available nodes. This flexible criterion allows connections to include nodes with unknown available (score = 0), which enables the subsequent GCN model to evaluate and refine the connectivity. This approach supports better continuity in the network and accommodates areas with incomplete or uncertain data.

2.3. Pedestrian Network Prediction Model

We use a graph-based learning approach to refine the pedestrian network and improve connectivity. This model is designed to predict complete pedestrian networks, with a particular focus on bridging missing or weakly connected pathways. The model can learn spatial relationships by leveraging graph topology and proximity-based features to infer pedestrian connections.

The architecture utilises a GCN that leverages graph connectivity, as outlined in Section 2.2, to aggregate contextual information from neighbouring nodes. It consists of two stacked graph convolution layers, and each layer is followed by a ReLU activation function. This configuration allows the model to assess availability based on adjacent available areas, which is possible even in regions where data may be incomplete or fragmented.

This graph-based design ensures that the model benefits from relational information, which promises robustness in cases of sparse or incomplete pedestrian data. Using a regression-based approach, the model calculates an availability score for each potential pedestrian link, which represents the likelihood of a valid connection.

3. Results

Utilising the GCN model to predict availability scores across a 2m resolution grid network, which generates a continuous surface of availability potential throughout the study area. Figure 3(a) illustrates the results, highlighting predicted available segments across the study area. The scores are standardised on a scale from 0 to 1, where higher values indicate available areas, such as parks and sidewalks. By contrast, lower values represent non-available areas, including buildings and restricted zones. Only grid cells with availability scores above 0.6 are shown on the map to improve visual clarity, which highlights significant pedestrian paths and removes low-score distractions. The fine resolution of the grid leads to dense clusters of high-scoring segments, which appear as dark, path-like formations when viewed at scale. The results demonstrate notable improvements in pedestrian network completeness by predicting available areas not present in the original datasets.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Model-predicted pedestrian availability and qualitative evaluation of fragmented areas: (a) Distribution of predicted pedestrian availability scores across the study area; (b) Comparison of fragmented areas A and B (original and predicted). The left panels show input

pedestrian infrastructure (original datasets), while the right panels present predicted availability. Insets A1–B2 illustrate model-inferred paths that connect previously unlinked segments. Corresponding street-level images (right column) validate both successful and partial predictions, including informal alleys (A1, A2) and sidewalk-less passages (B1, B2).

Beyond visual assessment, we conduct a quantitative evaluation of model performance on the test dataset. Predicted availability scores are binarised using a 0.6 threshold, which classifies cells with scores ≥ 0.6 as available and < 0.6 as non-available. This threshold is selected empirically to prioritise precision, reducing the risk of misclassifying non-available areas as available. Based on Equations (1)–(3), the model achieves 81.6% accuracy and 91.5% precision for available areas, while recall is lower at 45.2%, reflecting a conservative prediction strategy. In the equations, true positives (TP) refer to the correct predication of available areas; false positives (FP) are non-available areas incorrectly identified as available; true negatives (TN) are correctly prediction of non-available areas; and false negatives (FN) are available areas incorrectly classified as non-available.

$$accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FP+TN+FN} \quad (1)$$

$$precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (2)$$

$$recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3)$$

To further assess the model’s performance in fragmented or informal environments, we conduct a qualitative evaluation in two regions, A and B, where mapped pedestrian paths are absent in the input data. Figure 3(b) shows many high-score predictions aligned with visually confirmed pedestrian environments, including informal connections (A1) and alleys (A2, B2) validated using Google Street View, which are typically omitted in official datasets. This suggests that the model can infer pedestrian availability beyond the labelled data. However, some predictions are not successfully achieved. For example, the model fails to identify an available segment in B1, possibly due to limited topological continuity or sparse neighbouring connections within the graph structure, which may have reduced the confidence in assigning high pedestrian availability. Despite this, the model still successfully captured adjacent available areas, such as the alley running south of B1 and the intersection in the middle to the east connecting multiple narrow segments, demonstrating a partial recognition of informal environments. These findings highlight the model’s strength in extending pedestrian availability detection beyond official datasets, making the method particularly valuable

for pedestrian dynamics, walkability analysis, infrastructure mapping, urban planning improvements.

4. Conclusions

This study introduces a graph-based pedestrian network model that uses GCN to enhance pedestrian availability analysis. The model integrates various spatial features and utilises a fine-scale grid. Thus, it effectively overcomes the limitations of traditional pedestrian datasets, which typically suffer from fragmentation and missing connections. The findings show that this approach improves pedestrian network construction approach, which ensures accurate modelling of well-connected available areas.

Apart from enhancing pedestrian networks, this framework also holds potential for advancing pedestrian dynamics and enabling broad real-world improvements. It supports infrastructure planning by identifying walkway gaps, which provides precise insights into pedestrian dynamics from targeted improvements to the built environment. It also enables personalised navigation solutions that address mobility constraints or physical barriers and adapts to individual preferences, which enhances availability for diverse pedestrian needs. Furthermore, the flexibility of the approach allows the integration of distinctive local urban elements such as Taiwan's arcade-style sidewalks. This combination advances human-centred design principles within complex urban systems.

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